

Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

D3.2: Training manual on the use and local testing of the collection platform

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Executive Summary

This document presents the deliverable D3.2: 'Training manual on the use and local testing of the collection platform', which focuses on a specific subsystem of the LET'S CARE Hub platform, namely the tool *Le Sphinx*, which is utilized for the collection of quantitative data. It is a subsystem of the Let's Care Hub platform. For detailed information about it, please refer to deliverable D1.5:

'LET'S CARE Hub platform'.

The manual supports in effectively implementing quantitative surveys designed to explore key factors impacting Safe Education outcomes.

The questionnaire is developed based on the Safe Education Theoretical Model, ensuring that data collection aligns with the project's research goals. *Le Sphinx* was selected for its robust features that facilitate survey design, data management, and compliance with data privacy standards.

Beyond technical instructions, the manual offers practical guidance for field use, including troubleshooting tips and insights gathered from early testing phases. Importantly, it connects the survey data to the broader aims of the project by explaining how collected evidence will inform future policy recommendations and educational models.

1. Introduction

This document serves as a manual for utilizing *Le Sphinx*, the LET'S CARE quantitative data collection platform, designed to support the implementation of the questionnaire aimed at analysing the interactions among the main determinants of Safe Education outcomes. It presents the key functionalities of the tool and the necessary guidance to effectively support the data collection within the LET'S CARE project.

The first part of the document presents the design of the questionnaire, which is built upon the Safe Education Theoretical Model. The following sections focus on the data collection process. First, the key features required in a data collection tool are discussed, followed by an introduction to *Le Sphinx* and its core functionalities. The manual explains how to use the tool, create survey sections, select question types, and define levels of measurement. It also includes a troubleshooting section and feedback from initial testing phases to help users manage common issues. The document concludes by showing how the survey results will be used to support evidence-based policy and educational models and outlines the next steps in the LET'S CARE project.

1. Design of the questionnaire

1.1. Safe Education Theoretical Model design

The questionnaires proposed for the quantitative data collection are embedded in a structured, theory-driven framework organized around key Pillars that correspond to different systemic levels – ranging from micro-level (P1: students), meso-level (P2: teachers), exo-level (P3: headmasters), to the macro-level (P4: policymakers) - designed to operationalize and measure the multidimensional and systemic concept of Safe Education (Berastegui et al., 2021). This conceptual model emerges in response to specific informational and analytical needs identified at both academic and policy levels, aiming to produce a nuanced and actionable understanding of educational safety, particularly for populations at heightened risk of exclusion. The development of these instruments is the result of a robust methodological process that integrates theoretical foundations, empirical insights, and participatory contributions, ensuring both conceptual rigor and field relevance.

The construction of the questionnaires followed three sequential and interconnected stages:

1. Systematic Literature Reviews

The process began with three systematic literature reviews, two of which have already been published (Di Lisio et al., 2025; Dias et al., 2024). These reviews aimed to synthesize current knowledge on how relationships with family, peers, and teachers—as well as the overall school climate—affect school engagement, academic underachievement, and early school leaving, particularly among children at risk of social exclusion. By identifying both hindering and promoting factors, the reviews provided a solid theoretical foundation for the development of the Safe Education Theoretical Model. They also enabled the mapping of key constructs and revealed gaps in the existing evidence base. Moreover, the reviews supported the identification of previously validated scales and measurement instruments used in earlier studies, which were then evaluated for their relevance and applicability within the model. This foundational phase ensured that the Safe Education Theoretical Model was firmly grounded in the most up-to-date and peer-reviewed scholarship, while also pinpointing areas in need of further investigation.

2. Qualitative Fieldwork

To complement and expand upon the insights derived from the literature, an extensive qualitative research phase was undertaken across the countries participating in the LET'S CARE project. This stage was critical in ensuring that the model captured not only theoretically established variables but also those emerging directly from the lived realities of key stakeholders. The qualitative component included:

- 24 Semi-structured interviews with families, aimed at understanding the conditions that foster or hinder children's sense of safety and belonging within educational settings.
- 12 Focus groups with teachers, to explore institutional and relational dimensions of educational safety from a professional perspective.
- 12 Life history interviews with NEET youth, to trace retrospectively the experiences of those who had disengaged from education, uncovering the processes that contributed to educational vulnerability.

The narratives and themes emerging from these activities were systematically coded and analyzed, providing a rich empirical layer to the model and contributing to the creation of original variables not previously identified in the literature.

3. Co-creation, Validation and Triangulation

The initial construction of the model was based on a selection of variables identified through preliminary desk and empirical research. These variables were subsequently operationalized into measurement instruments selected according to their applicability to target populations, as well as their reliability and validity (Resnick & Inguito, 2011; Souza et al., 2017). The resulting four surveys underwent a rigorous, multi-step validation process to ensure their applicability and contextual sensitivity:

- Co-creation workshops were organized with stakeholders, including field researchers, practitioners, and target-group representatives, to refine the variables and questionnaire structure. Their feedback was instrumental in adjusting language, scope, and cultural appropriateness.
- Content validation by disciplinary experts was then conducted using a Delphi methodology, where scholars in education, psychology, sociology, and migration studies reviewed the proposed variables and provided iterative feedback on clarity, relevance, and coherence.
- Cross-cultural validation and triangulation took place in collaboration with implementing partners in each country, to ensure that the tools would be suitable for deployment in diverse educational systems and sociocultural contexts.
 - Cognitive Interviews with Children: Reflecting the model's child-centered approach, the student questionnaires underwent pre-testing through cognitive interviews with children from all targeted age groups. Based on the feedback gathered, the instruments were subsequently adapted to enhance clarity, relevance, and developmental appropriateness.

Special attention was also given to sociodemographic variables and adapted scales, whose formulation was discussed and harmonized across countries through consensus-building processes.

This step was essential to secure comparability across diverse contexts while preserving local specificity.

The outcome of this multistage, co-created process is a set of four tailored questionnaires —one each for headmasters (P3) and teachers (P2), and two adapted versions for children (P1)—alongside a set of policy-level indicators designed for completion by policymakers (P4). Together, these instruments form the systemic Safe Education Theoretical Model.

1.2. The Four Questionnaires

In this chapter, we will present the four types of questionnaires (Teacher, Headmaster, Student – Older children, Student – Younger children) that have been developed to collect data for analysing the existing interactions among the main indicators and determinants affecting Safe Education. All questionnaires were originally developed in English and translated into the six languages of the Field Work Partners (Bulgarian, Polish, Lithuanian, Italian, Portuguese and Spain). Below, we provide a brief overview of each questionnaire. To end, a detailed example of the composition of the sections for the teachers' questionnaire is provided.

1.2.2. Students

Older children (12-18 years old) version

It starts with an introduction and a consent form, followed by five sections. There are 44 close-ended questions and 3 open-ended questions. The questions cover the following topics:

- Personnel characteristics
- Family, home and caregivers
- Well-being
- Relationships with family and caregivers
- Relationship with friends
- Relationships with classmates
- Relationships with teachers
- Educational and school experience

Younger children (8-11 years old) version

It starts with an introduction and a consent form, followed by five sections. There are 26 close-ended questions, 2 open-ended questions and 1 mixed question. The questions cover the following topics:

- Personnel characteristics

- Family, home and caregivers
- Well-being
- Relationships with family and caregivers
- Relationship with friends
- Relationships with classmates
- Relationships with teachers
- Educational and school experience

1.2.3. Teacher

It starts with an introduction and a consent form, followed by six sections. There are 34 close-ended questions and 2 open-ended questions that require numerical answers. The questions cover the following topics:

- Personnel characteristics
- Job-related characteristics
- Training and professional development
- Educational practices
- Self-perceived efficacy
- Job satisfaction and social vocation
- Work distress
- Developmental relationships with students and assessment of safety
- Attachment with the students
- School environment

1.2.4. Headmaster

It starts with an introduction and a consent form, followed by six sections. There are 54 close-ended questions and 8 open-ended questions that require numerical answers. The questions cover the following topics:

- Personnel characteristics
- Employment information
- School characteristics
- Environment adequacy and availability of resources
- Order and discipline
- Structural organization
- School staff's training and professional development

- Teaching and Learning
- Community partnership
- Connectedness
- Quality of interpersonal relationships
- Respect for diversity
- Physical and emotional safety

1.2.5. Structure of the questionnaires

Each questionnaire is structured into different sections according to content, with a personalised design depending on the specific areas we aim to investigate with each type of informant. The teacher's questionnaire is used as an example to illustrate how these sections are organised:

- Section 1: Introduction to the questionnaire and consent to participate;
- Section 2: Personnel characteristics (gender, age, ethnic minority status, disability/hampered health, country of origin, migrant background) and job-related characteristics (educational level, work experience, current work status, employment status, teacher instruction cycle, teaching subject, teaching subject);
- Section 3: Training and professional development (teaching in multicultural settings; teaching training on competencies and diversity, quality of teacher training, need for professional development for teaching for diversity, professional development barriers);
- Section 4: Educational practices (cognitive activation, teacher's ongoing assessment, promotion and collaboration, adaptation of instruction, disciplinary climate, the management of the classroom climate);
- Section 5: Self perceived efficacy in multicultural and diversity classroom, in student engagement, in instruction;
- Section 6: Job satisfaction and social vocation (social utility, job satisfaction with profession, teacher's job security, sense of purpose);
- Section 7: Work distress (workload stress, work overload);
- Section 8: Developmental relationship with students and assessment of safety (developmental relationship with the students, teacher's assessment of student safety, attachment to the students);
- Section 9: School's practices (transformational leadership, diversity practice).

2. *Le Sphinx* tool to collect quantitative data

2.1. Key features for the choice of data collection software

The essential features required for the software to adequately meet the data collection needs of the LET'S CARE project have been decided following the criteria summarized below. These key features serve as the foundation for ensuring the software meets the necessary functionalities for large-scale and cross-country data collection purposes.

The principal features required include:

1. The capacity to include the informed consent procedures as well as the associated collection, management, and storage of personal data in a safe manner that accomplishes GDPR requirements.
 - a. Personal data needs to be anonymized or at least pseudonymized. To that end, a method to generate unique identifiers per user that could allow the combination of all questionnaire answers in one database for analyses will be necessary.
 - b. The potential need to present different formats of information and consent clauses (i.e., adapted to children under consent age vs. adults).
2. The necessity to design a sorting procedure to guide each respondent profile to their corresponding questionnaire (including younger and older children, teachers, and headmasters).
 - a. The capacity to change the questionnaire language in a responsive way to adapt to fieldwork in different countries. While the translation of questionnaires in T2.3 will be managed as part of cross-cultural validation, the data collection tool must allow multi-language input for all questions in a single database. The working language (master version of the questionnaire) needs to be English.
 - b. Various response formats will be required (matrix, multiple responses, open answers, numeric entries, limiting answer options, etc.).
3. For fieldwork quality control and data monitoring, the system should conduct online statistics and allow to perform quality checks (e.g., number of questionnaires by country, completion rates, etc.).

We chose *Le Sphinx* over other alternatives because it offers greater flexibility and better meets the specific needs of our study. Unlike other platforms that limit the number of cases or impose other constraints, *Le Sphinx* allows an unlimited number of respondents per project, an essential feature given our estimated sample size of approximately 21,000 participants, including children, teachers and headmasters.

Additionally, *Le Sphinx* offers the essential feature of anonymizing or pseudonymizing personal data from the beginning, ensuring the privacy and confidentiality of participant responses. This aspect is particularly significant for our research, which involves collecting sensitive data, necessitating the highest level of privacy protection for participants.

2.2. Introduction to the Le Sphinx Software

Le Sphinx is a survey, analysis and data visualisation software. Detailed information about the software and a comprehensive usage guide can be found on the company's website, where users can access numerous video tutorials explaining how to use the software, and an E-learning course.

Le Sphinx allows the creation of professional surveys, analyses of the quantitative and qualitative data and the presentation of the results via interactive dashboards and reports. Moreover, it provides a range of products and options tailored to users' needs, objectives, and usage requirements. Among all the products, we opted for the IQ3 Software for survey creation and data analysis, that better aligns with the LET'S CARE project's goals. IQ3 Software offers solutions for every research phase, including survey programming, distribution, importing external data, data management, statistical analysis, text analysis, and data visualisation. Moreover, it offers multiple distribution channels and formats, making it versatile for different needs, it ensures respondents anonymity, and it supports various languages.

2.3. Le Sphinx functionalities

In this paragraph, we explain how to use the key functionalities of *Le Sphinx* across three main phases: before data collection (questionnaire design), during data collection (distribution and response gathering, monitoring of data with dashboards), and after data collection (analysis of results and data management).

2.4. Questionnaire design

First steps

The first step in creating a survey is to download the IQ3 software. The IQ3 desktop software is required to program and design surveys and manage the data. Once finalized, the survey is exported to *Le Sphinx Online*, which enables the distribution of the survey, the real-time data collection and the data analysis. Instructions for installing the software and activating the license can be found in the online manual provided by Le Sphinx.

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When the software is opened, the left sidebar displays the main screen with three options available to users (Le Sphinx Iberoamérica. (n.d.); Figure 1):

- **"Create a study"**: allows users to create a study from scratch, by copying and pasting questions (in text format), or by using an existing study as a starting point.
- **"Open a study"**: enables users to work on an existing study.
- **"SphinxOnline"**: allows users to connect to the SphinxOnline platform, which offers a set of distribution features (email, SMS, tablets, QR code, and campaign tracking) and tools for online analysis (DATAVIV').

Figure 1: left sidebar of the Sphinx iQ3 software

By clicking on the New Survey option, a window appears where users can enter information regarding the survey title, select the language, and apply models and styles (Figure 2).

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The screenshot shows a 'New survey' window with the following sections:

- Properties:**
 - Title (present in this form's banner):
 - Comment:
 - Body: Period:
- Languages and translations:**
 - Choose the survey language and its translations
 - Current language: English - EN
- Models and styles:**
 - Apply models and styles
 - Default logo: (none)

Navigation buttons at the bottom: << Previous, Next >>, Finish, Cancel. There are also left and right arrow buttons in the 'Models and styles' section.

Figure 2: new survey window

As shown in Figure 3, the settings permit the selection of a primary language and the translation of the survey into additional languages. The master version of the questionnaire is in English and is also implemented in other languages to accommodate the fieldwork across all countries where the study is conducted (Bulgaria, Italy, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Spain).

Figure 3: the languages and translations options

To write the questionnaire, the user must be familiar with certain methodological foundations.

Question format

Survey questions can be classified according to the following groups (Fowler, 2013; Fink, 2015):

- **Closed vs open questions:**

- Closed questions: a list of accessible responses is provided to the respondent. For example: Educational level - “What is the highest level of formal education you have completed? (Choose the one that best suits your situation): 1. Bachelor’s Degree; 2. Master’s Degree; 3. Doctoral Degree (Ph.D.)”

The benefits of using closed questions lie in the fact that they offer a more efficient method of gathering data. This is because respondents can more easily answer questions when given response options, and researchers can better understand the meaning of the responses, analyse data, and interpret the findings. Additionally, closed questions help avoid the issue of respondents providing rare answers that may not be analytically useful.

- Open questions: the acceptable responses are not provided exactly to the respondent. For example: Age - “How old are you”?

Open-ended questions offer several benefits. They allow researchers to gather unexpected answers, providing insights into respondents' genuine opinions in their own words. Respondents can answer in their own words, capturing variations that

predefined options might miss. Open questions are especially useful when there are too many possible answers to list for respondents.

In turn, closed questions can be categorised into the following groups (Toepoel, 2016; Fowler, 2013; Fink 2015):

- Boolean questions:
 - Agree/disagree: typically, respondents are presented with a statement and asked whether they agree (their feelings align closely with the statement) or disagree with it (they strongly differ from the statement). While this format is useful for gathering responses to complex statements, it also comes with several drawbacks, such as limitations in ordering people in the middle of a continuum.
For example: Assent to participate - “Do you agree to participate? Yes, I agree. No, I do not agree”.
 - Yes/no: similarly to the previous case, these methods are simple to employ and assess. However, a small misunderstanding could lead to the respondent's answer being completely opposite to their actual intention. Additionally, in certain situations, requesting exclusively positive or negative opinions may cause participants to decline to respond or opt for a "don't know" response.
For example: Quality of Teacher Training - “Thinking of all of your professional development activities (such as mentoring, training, secondments), during the last 12 months, did any of these have a positive impact on your teaching practice?: 1. Yes; 2. No; 3. I haven't received any training”.
- Ordinal scales: are especially helpful when there's a clear idea or concept for which an evaluative answer is needed. They are structured options that follow a sequence, starting from one pole and progressing through intermediate choices to the opposite pole. Respondents are required to assess the provided labels, reflect on their own sentiments or views, and select the appropriate category accordingly. They can involve verbal labels (e.g., from "totally disagree" to "totally agree") or polar point labels, such as numbers from 1 to 10.
For example: Disciplinary climate - “How strongly do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the class where you spend the most time? [Strongly disagree (1) / Disagree (2) / Agree (3) / Strongly agree (4)]: 1. When the lesson begins, I have to wait quite a long time for students to quieten down; 2. Students in this class take care to create a pleasant learning atmosphere; 3. I lose quite a lot of time because of students interrupting the lesson; 4. There is much disruptive noise in this classroom”.

- Nominal scales: usually, they list different categories. However, there is often a risk of not including all the possible categories. To address this, the category "other" is frequently added. *For example:* Gender - "Are you... 1. Male; 2. female; 3. Other; 4. Prefer not to answer".

Create a section

Before creating any content within the questionnaire, and to support the structure of our quantitative data collection, it has been helpful to first create sections to organise the questionnaire layout. To add a section, go to the "Home" menu or the "Insert" menu and click on "Section." (Figure 4).

Figure 4: create a new section toolbar

A dialog box will open, allowing users to add new instructions, define display conditions, and customize them. These features are divided into two tabs: Definition and Controls (Figure 5).

Figure 5: new section window

Create a question

Creating a question means specifying its properties, including the label, variable type (single choice, multiple choice, scale, text, numeric, date...), and response methods for closed-ended questions (Le Sphinx Iberoamérica. (n.d.)).

To create a question, go to the "Home" menu or the "Insert" menu and click on "Question." (Figure 6).

Figure 6: create a new question toolbar

A dialog box will open where you can define certain properties (label, variable name, question type, response option titles, etc.) (Figure 7). The Definition tab allows users to write the question text, define the variable name, its type, and the response method. The Controls tab allows users to set a condition for displaying the question based on a specific profile, to make the response mandatory. The Calculation tab allows users to create calculated variables (Le Sphinx Iberoamérica. (n.d.)). The "Other" box allows users to add a free-text field to collect a response not listed among the predefined

options, effectively turning it into an open-text question. It is possible to make the response mandatory by checking the corresponding box.

Figure 7: create a new question window

Filter and Jumps options

In cross-cultural contexts such as the LET'S CARE project, it was necessary to filter the response options according to the specific countries in which the survey was conducted. This was achieved by clicking on the *Display conditions* option in the *Modalities* section of the *Controls* window (Figure 8).

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Figure 8: create a new question toolbar

This made it possible, for example, to assign each response option, representing the schools participating in the project, to their respective country (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Display condition window

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The Jumps option allows to skip a set of questions based on the respondent's profile and go directly to another question. It is particularly useful when a group of questions does not apply to a specific segment of the respondents (Le Sphinx Iberoamérica. (n.d.); Figure 10).

The screenshot shows a software interface window titled "7. disability_yn" with three tabs: "Definition", "Controls", and "Calculation". The "Controls" tab is active. It contains three main sections: "Display", "Validation", and "Modalities".

- Display:** Includes a checkbox for "Show only if..." and a text input field for "Special instruction:".
- Validation:** Includes a checked checkbox for "Mandatory response" and another checked checkbox for "Jumps". The "Jumps" configuration shows a dropdown menu set to "if", a text field containing "7. disability_yn among 'Yes'", and a "Modify..." button. Below this, a "Go to" dropdown menu is set to "8. disability_extent". There is also an "Alert message:" text input field.
- Modalities:** Includes a "Display conditions" dropdown menu with an ellipsis icon, and two unchecked checkboxes: "Random order except for" and "Sort by alphabetical order".

At the bottom of the window, there are navigation arrows (left and right), a "New question" dropdown menu, a "Library" dropdown menu, and "OK" and "Cancel" buttons.

Figure 10: the Jumps function

We also used this function in the informed consent section, ensuring that when the response to consent is "no," the survey is automatically closed (Figure 11).

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Figure 11: the Jumps function in the assent consent

Integrating GDPR compliance

Ensuring compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is essential when collecting personal data through surveys. For this purpose, the results can be anonymized to ensure the privacy of survey participants, as depicted in Figure 12, and unique identifiers for users can be generated, allowing for the combination of all questionnaire answers into a single database for analysis, as shown in Figure 13.

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Figure 12: the respondent identification option

ently_live_in	6. CLE	7. DATE_SAISIE
	H2LT-2FDP	03/18/2024 10:4
	NKQK-G76V	03/18/2024 10:4
	JUGK-LP9X	03/18/2024 10:4
	ZL4P-LGGZ	03/18/2024 17:2
	Q6U4-GY7Y	03/18/2024 17:2

Figure 13: the visualisation of anonymized Identifiers

Furthermore, participation in the survey is subject to informed consent: users can only access the questionnaire if they respond “Yes.” If they select “No,” the survey automatically ends (Figure 13).

10. Do I have rights? How can I exercise them?

Yes, of course. In the first place, you can always decide to stop your participation.

In addition, you have other rights, such as:

- Ask us for more information.
- Ask us to know what information we have on you.
- Ask us to delete information.
- Ask us to make correct the information.
- Ask us to see the data we have collected and obtain a copy.

However, we keep your identifying codes for this activity only until we will have collected all the information we need from you and your fellow students. This means that after that it will be difficult to make corrections or to delete your information from the survey.

If you have questions about this, you can contact us in this way:

- Universidad Pontificia Comillas: C/Alberto Aguilera, 23, 28015 Madrid +34915422800 email: lets care@comillas.edu
- Principal Investigators: Mercedes Fernández García mercedes@comillas.edu Ana Berástegui Pedro-Viejo a.berastegui@comillas.edu Isabel Muñoz San Roque isabelmsanroque@comillas.edu

If you contact us and you are not happy, you can submit a complaint to the competent national data protection authority, in this case, the Spanish DPA (<https://www.aepd.es/en>). Because of language barriers, you could ask your local data protection authority (you can find your local data protection authority contact details following this link: https://edpb.europa.eu/about-edpb/about-edpb/members_en#member-at) for help. Nevertheless, we will always try to avoid that you need to do this, by answering your questions and helping you out whenever we can.

11. What do I do if I have questions?

If you or your child have any questions or suggestions, you can tell them to the LET'S CARE researchers who are present or contact us later at [Add name and contact details of fieldwork partner and the specific person in charge for LET'S CARE]. You can also tell your child's teacher or the contact point of your child's school.

Do you agree to participate?

Figure 13: the survey consent form

2.5. Distribution and data collection

Publish the questionnaire

To generate a link for respondents to access the survey, users must first publish their survey in the LeSphinx repository. To do this, users should navigate to File → Internet → Publish (Figure 1). A prompt will then appear (Figure 2), allowing users to publish the study on the LeSphinx online repository.

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To generate a link for respondents to access the survey, users must first publish it to the LeSphinx online repository. This can be done by navigating to File → Internet → Publish (Figure 14). A prompt will then appear (Figure 15), allowing users to complete the publication process and make the survey accessible online.

Figure 14: the Publish option

Users must use the Publish URL, username, and password provided during registration with LeSphinx. This information is available in the confirmation email. Next, users should click Next through all the steps to complete the publication process. Once finished, a final window will appear.

Figure 14: publication process prompt

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By clicking OK (Figure 15), users will be redirected to their LeSphinx Online account, where they can monitor the progress of the survey (Figure 16).

Figure 15: publication process final window

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Figure 16: survey progress monitoring page

Create custom quality control variables

To customize quality control, specific variables should be created to ensure accurate data monitoring. To create the IDEM (used to identify duplicate responses) and POSITION (provides additional clarity by indicating which duplicate was removed) variables, the Data Preparation menu should be accessed again by selecting > Data > Remove duplicates (Figure 17).

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Figure 17: Data Preparation menu

Then Select>Identify duplicates > click on all questions> and select order of saving (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Locate/delete duplicates options

Then, to create the variable SINGULARITY (N and % of problematic observation across time and by country), click on >Identify irrelevant observations (data) > Keep all variables selected > Mark all checks and set the requirement level one point closer to high (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Locate/delete duplicates options

To create the variable QUALITY (that calculates the mean quality across all cases in each dataset) ensure that the check is marked (Figure 20).

Figure 20: create the Quality variable

Now all these variables should appear in the end of the variables list (Figure 21).

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Figure 21: variables list

Visualize data with the dashboards

By clicking on the chart from the Le Sphinx homepage, the analysis facilities can be accessed (Figure 22).

Status	Responses		Date of creation	Last answer	
	Olderchildren	1398		19 Mar 2025	16 Jun 2025 11:50
	LestCare_survey_Y...	988		14 Mar 2025	16 Jun 2025 13:26
	Teachers	267		18 Mar 2025	16 Jun 2025 12:05
	Teacherinformedco...	320		19 Mar 2025	16 Jun 2025 11:25
	LetsCare_Survey_P...	0		24 Mar 2025	

Figure 22: Le Sphinx homepage

Then, users can have access to the report they have already started (Monthly summaries in this case), or they can create a new one, clicking on New visualisation.

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Figure 23: Report options

The user can select an Empty view, to create dashboards from scratch, or select an existing one (Figure 24).

Figure 24: new visualisation option

Afterwards, users have to give a name and click on ok (Figure 25).

New visualization ×

General Calculation Display Colors Style

Name Field required

Description

Password free access [Control access](#)

Access to survey results is not restricted.
This view is readable in runtime mode without a password.

Allow view export

Allow batch export for all answer options of the variable

Automatic report: generate a report with all the variables of my study

Cross them with the variable:

< Previous ✓ OK × [Cancel](#)

Figure 25: new visualisation option

On the left, all of the variables of the survey can be seen. On the right, there are specific functionalities to analyse the data. On the top of the screen there are some general tools, and on the bottom the pages manager. On the center of the page tables and graphics related to the data that wanted to be analysed can be added.

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The screenshot displays the DATAVIV data visualization platform. On the left, a list of variables is shown, including 'id1', 'assent_consent', 'sur_country', 'student_code', and a section 'SECTION_A_You_and_your_bac...' containing variables like 'gender', 'age', 'gender_bul', 'class_code', 'sur_school1', 'ethnicity', 'disability_yn', 'health', 'sex_orien', 'cob', 'cob_Other', 'sex_orien_opt', 'born_sur_country', 'cob_spa', 'cob_spa_Other', 'cob_bul', 'cob_bul_Other', 'cob_ita', 'cob_ita_Other', 'cob_lit', 'cob_lit_Other', 'cob_pol', 'cob_pol_Other', 'cob_parent1', 'cob_parent1_Other', 'cob_por', 'cob_por_Other', 'length_stay', 'cob_parent1_spa', 'cob_parent1_spa_...', 'cob_parent1_bul', 'cob_parent1_bul_O...', 'cob_parent1_ita', 'cob_parent1_ita_Ot...', 'cob_parent1_lit', 'cob_parent1_lit_Ot...', 'cob_parent2', 'cob_parent2_Other', 'cob_parent1_pol', and 'cob_parent1_pol O'. The central area features a large '+ Drag a question here to add a view filter' prompt and a list of visualization options: 'One-way table', 'Cross analysis', 'Advanced analysis', 'Custom table', 'Textual and semantic analysis', 'View filter', 'Text', 'Image', and 'Shape'. The right panel, titled 'Information', provides instructions: 'Select an object to edit its properties' and 'Click the + button to add new objects', followed by three numbered steps: 1. Choose the best visualization for your data; 2. Set calculation methods and display options; 3. Interact with your views. The bottom status bar shows 'Polish', 'Strona 1', and navigation icons.

Figure 26: data visualisation page

By drag and dropping the variables from the list, the related graphic will appear.

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Figure 27: graph example

On the right side of the screen, there are different options to modify the graph. Users can, for example, change the type of the chart or the colors of the graph.

To monitor data quality based on the previously described indicators, it is useful to create dedicated dashboards, as shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28: quality monitoring dashboards

2.6. Analysis of results and data management

To manage the collected data, users can click on the "Data Management" section from the software's start panel.

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Figure 29: Data Management section

To support this, Sphinx iQ3 offers a set of features that allow users to review responses, sort them, clean them, correct them, and enrich them by calculating new variables, among other tasks. The spreadsheet provides functions for sorting and filtering data, locking/unlocking entries, finding and replacing observations, transforming and combining variables, duplicating entries, merging surveys, exporting the data file, and more.

By clicking on Data → Export, it is possible to export the collected data for further analysis. In the dialog box that appears, the specific data to be included in the generated Excel file can be defined. It is possible to export only the data currently displayed on the screen or to export all observations. A directory must then be selected to save the Excel file.

The dataset can also be exported in SPSS or Triple-S format. This is done by accessing the "File" tab, selecting "Export", and choosing the appropriate format.

Figure 30: Data Export function

3. Troubleshooting section or user feedback from early testing

During the initial phase of data collection, several recurring issues were identified across all participating countries, regardless of language or type of informant: young children (from 9 to 11 years old), older children (from 12 to 18 years old), teachers and headmasters. The problems have been described in the Table below. These difficulties were consistently reported and addressed through collaborative review processes led by fieldwork partners, as well as technical adjustments to the LeSphinx platform to ensure optimal usability on both desktop and mobile devices.

The testing process began by sending the questionnaires to fieldwork partners in both digital format (via LeSphinx online) and as downloadable PDFs. This dual-format approach allowed partners to thoroughly review the content for potential translation errors while simultaneously testing the usability and functionality of the digital version. Feedback was collected through structured reporting, as well as follow-up emails and technical support calls when necessary.

Table 1. Type of problem and solution carried out

Type of problem	Solution
Translation errors	Partners received the initial link to the questionnaire in LeSphinx and in PDF. They corrected translation errors in the PDF (e.g., grammatical errors, inclusive language), and we adjusted the online version accordingly.
Display issues on devices	Some formatting problems occurred depending on the device used. The mobile version offered a poorer user experience, so we adjusted the layout for both desktop and mobile formats.
Problems with the Informed Consent section	The transition between pages did not work smoothly, and the presentation was sometimes difficult to follow due to the large amount of text. This issue was resolved by improving the formatting and introducing progress bars to guide participants through the process more intuitively, thus aiding in better reading and comprehension of the consent form.
Problems with using the Password to enter to the questionnaire	Passwords were initially added to the questionnaires to ensure that only the intended respondent could access them. However, several issues emerged with their use, including login errors and access difficulties. As a result, passwords were removed during the piloting phase to facilitate smoother participation.
Mismatch Between Scale Labels and Visual Indicators	In some cases, there was a mismatch between the verbal labels (e.g., “Disagree”) and the associated visual elements, such as colors or emoticons. For example, “Disagree” was sometimes paired with a green smiling face, which typically signifies agreement. This inconsistency caused confusion among participants and was resolved by adjusting the formatting to ensure that verbal labels, icons, and colors were aligned consistently across all versions.
Validation Messages	<i>Le Sphinx</i> allows the addition of validation messages that appear when it is not possible to proceed with the questionnaire due to an error. Error messages were added specifically for questions requiring the total number of students and their distribution by gender, in order to help users understand why they are unable to continue.
Ensuring Survey Saving	We were concerned that respondents might reach the end of the survey and forget to click the save button, which would result in the questionnaire being marked as incomplete. From a technical standpoint, we moved the save button from the toolbar to the center of the page, just below the thank-you message.

Table Modifications	In response to partners' experiences and feedback, the presentation of some tables was modified to make them easier to complete.
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4. Contribution of the survey data to policy recommendations and educational models

The results of the data collection will have two main impacts: first, they will contribute to empirically testing and refining the Safe Education theoretical model; second, they will provide a robust evidence-based for developing the LET'S CARE policy recommendations.

Direct feedback from students, teachers, headmasters and policymakers collected through surveys will provide invaluable insights into the lived experiences within schools and the systemic barriers that hinder engagement and achievement, possibly leading to Early School Leaving (ESL). Gathering data from stakeholders across different educational levels and contexts will help identify both challenges and strengths in various educational systems, regions or schools. This multi-perspective feedback will be especially valuable for understanding the needs of vulnerable groups. Ultimately, the policy recommendations will be driven by this comprehensive, systemic feedback, ensuring they are grounded in real-world evidence and responsive to challenges at multiple levels.

The quantitative analysis of survey responses will enable a systematic understanding of the educational landscape, from individual learners to institutional leadership, ultimately informing evidence-based policy recommendations.

Data collected from students (P1) will highlight critical gaps in their conditions, such as disparities in access to resources, support systems or learning environment – often varying by geographic location or socioeconomic status. These insights can guide targeted policy recommendations, such as infrastructure investment or resource allocation, with particular relevance for vulnerable groups at risk of ESL. Furthermore, cross-analysing the survey data allows for a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon and enables comparisons of the effectiveness of specific programs or educational contexts.

The possibility to disaggregate survey data by demographics (e.g., age, socioeconomic status, region) will enable the formulation of highly tailored policy recommendations. This ensures that proposed policies could be adapted to the diverse needs of different segments of the population or countries.

The data collected from the teachers (P2) will offer a clear picture of the teaching profession, including challenges, job satisfaction, relationship with students and perceived support from the

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school. This information will support recommendations aimed at improving teachers' working conditions, professional status, initial training and continuous professional development and capacity to foster student engagement. Combined with responses from headmasters (P3), this data will help identifying skill gaps and training needs, which will be crucial for shaping sustainable, effective educational strategies.

From a school management perspective, input from headmasters will provide valuable resources into how schools function as institutions: the implementation of educational initiatives, collaboration with families and communities, and the accessibility and use of resources. This level of feedback can guide decisions on resource allocation, technology integration, and accessibility improvements within educational models.

This layered, disaggregated quantitative analysis – from students to headmasters -will support the development of policy recommendations that are context-sensitive, equity focused, and grounded in real-world data. The model ensures that policies are responsive to challenges at every level of the education system, enhancing both national strategies and transnational cooperation.

5. Conclusion and next steps

In the upcoming steps, we will proceed with the data collection in real-world settings. Following data collection, we will work on the interpretation of the results obtained. The findings from using this tool and the gathered data will be shared in two deliverables: D3.3: Methodological report (2) School ethnographies and Quantitative data collection, and D3.4: Safe Education empirical model: Report on data analysis results. Finally, we will disseminate the findings and results both within the LET'S CARE Hub and potentially through a scientific article.

References

- Di Lisio, G., Milá, A., Halty Barrutieta, A., Berastegui Pedro-Viejo, A., Couso Losada, A., & Pitillas Salvá, C. (2025). Nurturing Bonds that Empower Learning: A Systematic Review of the Significance of Teacher-Student Relationship in Education. *Frontiers in Education*, 10. <https://doi.org/doi:10.3389/educ.2025.1522997>
- Dias, P., Veríssimo, L., Carneiro, A., & Duarte, R. (2024). The role of socio-emotional security on school engagement and academic achievement: systematic literature review. *Frontiers in Education*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2024.1437297>
- Fink, A. (2015). *How to conduct surveys: A step-by-step guide*. SAGE publications.
- Fowler Jr, F. J. (2013). *Survey research methods*. Sage publications.
- Le Sphinx Homepage. Retrieved May 14, 2024, from <https://www.lesphinx.es/?lang=en>
- Le Sphinx Iberoamérica. (n.d.). Sphinx iQ3 software manual. Retrieved June 11, 2025, from https://www.lesphinx.es/files/ugd/132b06_48aab046344942a4a1fb186839f6e54f.pdf?lang=en
- Le Sphinx Iberoamérica. YouTube channel. Retrieved May 14, 2024, from <https://www.youtube.com/@lesphinxiberoamerica>
- Les Sphinx. Videos. Retrieved May 14, 2024, from <https://www.lesphinx.es/videos?lang=en>
- LeSphinx. Moodle login page. Retrieved May 14, 2024, from <https://lesphinx.moodlecloud.com/login/index.php>
- Resnick, B. A., & Inguito, P. L. (2011). The Resilience Scale: Psychometric Properties and Clinical Applicability in Older Adults. *Archives of Psychiatric Nursing*, 25(1), 11–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apnu.2010.05.001>
- Souza, A. C. de, Alexandre, N. M. C., Guirardello, E. de B., Souza, A. C. de, Alexandre, N. M. C., & Guirardello, E. de B. (2017). Propriedades psicométricas na avaliação de instrumentos: avaliação da confiabilidade e da validade. *Epidemiologia e Serviços de Saúde*, 26(3), 649–659. <https://doi.org/10.5123/S1679-49742017000300022>
- Toepoel, V. (2016). Developing the Survey: Questions and Answers. *Doing Surveys Online*, 55, 19–38.